

RESIDUAL THERMAL STRESSES IN SEMICRYSTALLINE THERMOPLASTIC

MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Summary

The build-up of residual thermal stresses in semicrystalline thermoplastic matrix composites has been studied by following the curvature of unbalanced cross-ply composite strips during heating and cooling. When cooling poly(ethylene terephthalate)/graphite composites, the residual thermal stresses begin to build up at the start of crystallization. A large increase in curvature during cooling is found to correspond to the large amount of matrix shrinkage that occurs during crystallization. The results for nylon 66/graphite composites are similar. When cooling J Polymer (a DuPont polyamide copolymer)/graphite composites, however, the residual thermal stresses do not begin to build up until after crystallization is complete. The large matrix shrinkage during crystallization does not contribute to the residual thermal stresses, but because the expansion coefficient of J Polymer after crystallization is larger than it is for poly(ethylene terephthalate), the level of residual thermal stresses is still high. A third type of behavior is observed for polyetheretherketone/graphite composites. When cooling polyetheretherketone/graphite composites, the residual thermal stresses begin to build up during crystallization, but the large matrix shrinkage that occurs during crystallization does not lead to a large increase in curvature.

Introduction

The thermal expansion properties of typical matrices and high modulus fibers, such as graphite and Kevlar® aramid, are very different. On cooling during processing, there will be a considerable amount of differential thermal shrinkage, and the differential thermal shrinkage could potentially lead to a significant level of residual thermal stresses. The problem of residual thermal stresses is of particular importance to thermoplastic matrix composites, because in general, the differential shrinkage is higher than when working with thermoset epoxy composites. Within the class of thermoplastic matrices, the differential shrinkage is highest for semi-crystalline thermoplastic matrices [1].

One method for studying the build-up of residual thermal stresses in semicrystalline thermoplastic matrices is to construct unbalanced, two-ply, [0/90] composites. Strips of these composites will develop curvature that is related to the amount of residual thermal stresses. The use of cross-ply composite strips has already been applied by Bailey and co-workers [2-4] to study generation of thermal strains and transverse ply cracking. We have used the technique to study residual thermal stresses in one amorphous thermoplastic matrix and in one semicrystalline thermoplastic matrix [5]. In this paper, we use the cross-ply composite strip technique to study the build-up of residual thermal stresses in four semicrystalline thermoplastic matrices - poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET), nylon 66, J Polymer (a DuPont polyamide copolymer), and polyetheretherketone (PEEK). First, the temperature dependence of the curvature of cross-ply composite strips using each matrix is discussed and related to thermal and physical properties of the matrix. Second, a theoretical analysis using a modified bimetallic strip theory and the component properties of the matrices and the fibers is shown to be in good agreement with the data.

Materials and Methods

The PET/graphite, nylon 66/graphite, and J Polymer/graphite cross-ply composite strips were all made by filament winding around a steel plate. First, PET (Goodyear Cleartuf® PET type 1002A), nylon 66 (DuPont of Canada Dartek® film), and J Polymer (DuPont) were obtained in films about 0.1 mm thick. A steel plate was covered with a layer of the chosen film and then wrapped with a unidirectional layer of Union Carbide T300 graphite fibers. A second layer of film covered the fibers and a second unidirectional fiber wrap was put on perpendicular to the first fiber wrap. A third layer of film covered the second fiber wrap. Each completed plate was dried in a vacuum oven overnight at 130°C and then pressed in a vacuum bag for 20 min. at 0.5 MPa. The temperatures for pressing the PET, nylon 66, and J Polymer composites were 285°C, 280°C, and 310°C respectively. The plates were allowed to cool by removing from the press and letting them sit at room temperature. Cutting the resulting composites off the plates resulted in two 200 X 200 mm [0/90] cross-ply composites which were 0.6 mm thick. These two composites were cut into cross-ply composite strips about 175 mm long and 15 mm wide.

The PEEK/graphite cross-ply composite strips were made by hand layup using APC I PEEK/graphite thermoplastic composite prepreg obtained from ICI. Zero and 90 degree strips 75 X 15 mm were cut from the composite prepreg. Two-ply, [0/90] composites were laid up and pressed in a vacuum bag at 370°C for 15 min. No additional pressure, besides the vacuum pressure, was applied.

Fig. 1 - Parameters used for determination of the radius of curvature of an arc.

The radius of curvature, r , was determined by measuring the height, δ , and the chord length, l , of the arc formed by the composite strip (see Fig. 1) and using the formula

$$r = (l^2 + \delta^2)/2\delta \quad (1)$$

The height was measured with a traveling microscope and the length was measured with a steel ruler.

The pressure dilatometer that was used for the thermal expansion experiments was described elsewhere [6,7]. The dynamic mechanical analysis was done on a DuPont 1090 Thermal Analyzer. The differential scanning calorimetry was done on a DuPont 1090 Thermal Analyzer and a Mettler TA3000 System.

Results

From Timoshenko's analysis of bimetallic strips [8], it can be seen that the dimensionless curvature, defined as the strip thickness divided by the radius of curvature (h/r), is directly related to the amount of differential thermal shrinkage which can induce stresses (See Eq. (2) below). The temperature dependence of h/r for the four different semicrystalline thermoplastic matrices are given in Figs. 2-5 and discussed below.

PET/Graphite

The dimensionless curvature of PET/graphite cross-ply composite strips was presented elsewhere [5] and will be summarized here; the data for heating and cooling is given in Fig. 2. On heating, there is an increase in slope around 100°C and the dimensionless curvature drops to zero at 257°C. These features correlate with the glass transition (80-90°C) and the melting point (260°C) of PET measured by DSC. We note however, that the glass transition and the melting point measured by dilatometry are slightly different - 70°C and 270°C respectively (See Fig. 6).

Fig. 2 - Dimensionless curvature as a function of temperature while heating and cooling a PET/graphite cross-ply composite strip. Heating rate was 10°C/min and cooling rate was 1.5°C/min.

Fig. 3 - Dimensionless curvature as a function of temperature while heating and cooling a nylon 66/graphite cross-ply composite strip. Heating rate was 10°C/min and cooling rate was 1.5°C/min.

Fig. 4 - Dimensionless curvature as a function of temperature while heating and cooling a J Polymer/graphite cross-ply composite strip. Heating rate was 5°C/min and cooling rate was 1-3°C/min.

Fig. 5 - Dimensionless curvature as a function of temperature while heating and cooling a PEEK/graphite cross-ply composite strip. Heating rate was 5°C/min and cooling rate was 1-3°C/min.

Fig. 6 - Specific volume of poly(ethylene terephthalate) and J Polymer as a function of temperature at zero (atmospheric)-pressure. T_g 's are glass-transition temperatures, T_m 's are melting temperatures, and T_c 's are the crystallization temperatures on slow cooling from the melt. The dotted portions of the curves including T_c are typical specific volume versus temperature behaviors during cooling.

Fig. 7 - Differential scanning calorimetry while cooling PET/graphite, nylon 66/graphite, J Polymer/graphite, and PEEK/graphite composites. All were cooled from the melt at 1.5°C/min.

The dimensionless curvature on cooling from the melt at 1.5°C/min begins to increase around 240°C and rapidly increases until about 180°C. We suspect that the rapid rise is due to the large differential shrinkage that occurs while the matrix is crystallizing. The large shrinkage that occurs during the crystallization of PET is shown by the representative cooling curve in Fig. 6. On cooling from the melt, PET will supercool below the equilibrium melting point until crystallization at T_c results in a rapid drop in specific volume. We would like to identify T_c with the initiation of the increase in dimensionless curvature, but the dimensionless curvature begins to increase at 240°C while the onset of crystallization as measured by DSC is at 227°C (See Fig. 7). We suggest that the reason for this discrepancy is that the cross-ply composite strips were not heated very far above the melting point and that the ultimate temperature was not high enough to melt all the nucleation sites; on cooling the presence of nucleation sites reduced the supercooling. To test this suggestion, a series of PET/graphite samples were heated to a given temperature, held five min. and cooled. The onset of the crystallization peak as a function of the hold temperature is plotted in Fig. 8. When heated only to 265°C, as we did with the cross-ply composite strips, crystallization begins at 237°C. When heated to 300°C, however, crystallization does not begin until 228°C.

Below 180°C, there are two changes in the slope of the dimensionless curvature plot. Between 120°C and 60°C, there is a gradual increase in the slope. This increase in slope is related to changes in the expansion

Fig. 8 - Temperature for the onset of crystallization as a function of the hold temperature experienced by a PET/graphite sample. Before cooling from the hold temperature, the sample was held at that temperature for 5 min.

coefficient and the modulus of PET as it goes through its glass transition. The second slope change is at 60°C; it is a decrease and it is accompanied by acoustic emissions from the sample. This slope change is probably due to cracking of the matrix. After the sample has cooled to room temperature, cracks in the matrix parallel to the fibers in the 90 degree ply are easily visible.

Finally, we note the the dimensionless curvature shows a considerable degree of hysteresis during the first heating and cooling cycle. As presented below, we found some degree of hysteresis for each type of composite included in this study. We do not know the reasons for this hysteresis, but it is probably related to the sample cooling conditions. During sample preparation, the samples were kept flat by cooling under 0.5 MPa pressure and no matrix cracking was observed in the finished samples. The cooling during the dimensionless curvature experiment, however, was under no pressure and matrix cracking was sometimes observed.

Nylon 66/Graphite

The dimensionless curvature of a nylon 66/graphite cross-ply composite strip while heating and cooling is given in Fig. 3. On heating, the dimensionless curvature decreases linearly with temperature until 220°C. The decrease after 220°C is more gradual and it extrapolates to zero dimensionless

curvature at 251°C. This temperature agrees closely with the end of the melting peak in DSC. We find no evidence of a slope change caused by a glass transition. Either there was enough water in the nylon 66 matrix to lower the T_g to below room temperature, or the changes in the expansion coefficient and the modulus of nylon 66 as it passes through its glass transition do not cause a slope change in the dimensionless curvature plot. As pointed out in Ref. [1] the slope of the magnitude of the residual thermal stresses in unidirectional composites as a function of temperature is approximately equal to the product of the expansion coefficient of the matrix and the modulus of the matrix. If the expansion coefficient increase above T_g was balanced by an equivalent modulus decrease, then the slope of the dimensionless curvature plot would not change at T_g .

On cooling the dimensionless curvature begins to increase at 228°C. This temperature was found by extrapolating the three highest temperature points to zero dimensionless curvature. This onset temperature is close to the temperature for the onset of crystallization as measured by DSC which is 235°C (See Fig. 7). Furthermore, the large differential shrinkage which occurs during crystallization can tentatively be assigned as the cause of the rapid increase in dimensionless curvature at high temperatures. Below 150°C, the dimensionless curvature increases steadily and there is no indication of matrix cracking. Similar to the results for PET/graphite, there is a significant hysteresis in the dimensionless curvature during the first heating and cooling cycle.

J Polymer/Graphite

The dimensionless curvature of a J Polymer/Graphite cross-ply composite strip during heating and cooling is given in Fig. 4. The results on heating are similar to the results for PET/graphite and nylon 66/graphite. There is a steady decrease in dimensionless curvature and it extrapolates to zero at 298°C. Again, this temperature corresponds to the end of melting as determined by DSC. The dimensionless curvature also has a slope change around 130-140°C which is near the glass transition of J Polymer. In contrast to the PET/graphite results, however, the slope is lower above T_g rather than higher. Apparently, the increase in the expansion coefficient above the glass transition is less than the decrease in the modulus.

On cooling, there is no evidence of a rapid increase in dimensionless curvature due to the large differential shrinkage that occurs during crystallization. The reason is that unlike PET/graphite and nylon 66/graphite composites, the residual stresses in J Polymer/graphite composites do not begin to form until after crystallization is complete. The dimensionless curvature begins to increase at 240°C while as seen by DSC, the crystallization is complete at 243°C (See Fig. 7). The reason for the unique behavior of J Polymer composites is not known. We suspect the most likely explanation is that J Polymer is less crystalline than either PET or nylon 66. With a low enough amount of crystallinity, the crystallization may have to be complete before the matrix has enough stiffness to support residual stresses.

Slope changes in the dimensionless curvature during cooling can be explained by two effects. The glass transition of the matrix at 130-140°C causes a slope increase. Below 100°C, the gradual decrease in slope is probably due to matrix cracking. Finally, we note again a hysteresis in dimensionless curvature during the first heating a cooling cycle.

PEEK/Graphite

The dimensionless curvature of a PEEK/graphite cross-ply composite strip during heating and cooling is given in Fig. 5. On heating the dimensionless curvature decreases with a shoulder between 100-150°C. This shoulder is related to changes that occurs near the glass transition at 143°C [9]. Extrapolating the last three points of the heating data results in the dimensionless curvature reaching zero at 328°C. This point is near but slightly below the melting point of 332°C.

On cooling, the dimensionless curvature begins to increase at 319°C. The temperature for the onset of the increase was found by extrapolating the points above 200°C. This temperature is right in the middle of the DSC crystallization peak given in Fig. 7. Even though the residual thermal stresses are forming during crystallization, there is no rapid increase in the dimensionless curvature. We can speculate that the fibers effect the crystallization. They fibers might, for example, promote a crystal structure that reduces the amount of differential thermal shrinkage during crystallization. On continued cooling, the dimensionless curvature increases steadily with a slight decrease in slope near T_g . The change in slope near T_g is much smaller than the change that occurs near T_g while heating.

Discussion

The build-up of residual thermal stresses in semicrystalline thermoplastic matrix composites is dependent on the properties of the matrix. In some matrices (e.g. PET and nylon 66) the dimensionless curvature during cooling shows a rapid increase at high temperatures. In other matrices (e.g. J Polymer and PEEK) there is no such rapid increase. We have suggested that the rapid increases are due to the large differential shrinkage that occurs during crystallization. To support this suggestion, we have attempted a theoretical analysis of the dimensionless curvature using the properties of the fibers and the matrix. We will assume that the rapid increases observed in dimensionless curvature are caused by the differential shrinkage that occurs during crystallization. If our predictions match the experiment, this assumption will be confirmed.

An analysis of cross-ply composite strip curvature was presented elsewhere [5] and is summarized here. The cross-ply composite strip is an analog of a bimetallic strip. The dimensionless curvature can be predicted by extending Timoshenko's [8] bimetallic strip theory to include the temperature dependent properties of the composite plies. The extension is

$$\frac{h}{r} = \int_{T_0}^T \frac{24(\alpha_0 - \alpha_{90})}{(14 + n + 1/n)} dT \quad (2)$$

where h is the strip thickness, r is the radius of curvature, T_0 is the temperature for the onset of residual thermal stresses, T is the temperature, $n = E_0/E_{90}$, and α_0 , α_{90} , E_0 , and E_{90} are the thermal expansion coefficients and the moduli of the zero and 90 degree plies. α_0 and α_{90} will be calculated using the Schapery equations [10] which are exact for composites with isotropic fibers and adequate for composites with anisotropic fibers [11]. E_0 and E_{90} will be calculated using the mechanics of materials results [12]. The equations are:

$$\alpha_0 = \frac{E_L V_f \alpha_L + E_m(T) V_m \alpha_m(T)}{E_L V_f + E_m V_m} \quad (3)$$

$$\alpha_{90} = (1 + \nu_m) \alpha_m(T) V_m + (1 + \nu_f) \alpha_T V_f - \alpha_0 (\nu_m V_m + \nu_f V_f) \quad (4)$$

$$E_0 = E_m(T) V_m + E_L V_f \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{1}{E_{90}} = \frac{V_m}{E_m(T)} + \frac{V_f}{E_T} \quad (6)$$

where V_f and V_m are volume fractions of the fibers and the matrix, E_L and E_T are the longitudinal and transverse moduli of the fibers, ν_m and ν_f are the Poisson's ratios of the fibers and the matrix, α_L and α_T are the longitudinal and transverse expansion coefficients of the fibers, $\alpha_m(T)$ is the thermal expansion coefficient of the matrix, and $E_m(T)$ is the modulus of the matrix. All properties except $E_m(T)$ and $\alpha_m(T)$ will be assumed to be independent of temperature. The temperature dependence of $E_m(T)$ will be found by a dynamic mechanical analysis experiment. The temperature dependence of $\alpha_m(T)$ will be found by differentiating the zero (atmospheric)-pressure volume versus temperature data, $V_m(T)$, for the neat matrix:

$$\alpha_m(T) = (1/3) d(\ln V_m(T))/dT \quad (7)$$

We begin with PET/graphite cross-ply composite strips as an example of a system that exhibits a rapid rise in dimensionless curvature at high temperatures. The temperature independent properties are listed in Table I. The fiber volume fraction was determined by measuring the density of the cross-ply composite strip and the fiber properties come from the work of Adams et. al. [13-14]. $E_m(T)$ will be taken equal to the storage modulus of semicrystalline PET. That data is plotted in Fig. 9. The sample used for the DMA experiment was annealed overnight in a vacuum oven at 130°C and annealed an additional 15 hours at 160°C. The annealing treatments were done to maximize the crystallinity. The zero-(atmospheric) volume versus temperature data for PET is given in Fig. 6 [15]. The solid line is the expansion data during heating but we need the volume shrinkage data during cooling. We extract this data from the data in Fig. 6 using the following assumptions. First, we assume the temperature where the dimensionless curvature begins to increase, T_{start} , is equal to the onset of crystallization, T_c , and that the volume at T_{start} is equal to the volume found by extrapolating a fit to the melt data above 270°C down to T_{start} . Second, we assume that the end of crystallization, T_{end} , occurs at the first break in the dimensionless curvature versus temperature plot and the volume below T_{end} is given by the solid line data in Fig. 6. Finally, we assume that the large volume change that occurs during crystallization can be represented by a straight line fit between the specific volume at T_{start} and the specific volume at T_{end} . Using these assumptions, the complete volume versus temperature data for a cooling experiment can be written down using the fits to the solid line data given in Ref. [15].

The results of a zero-parameter, modified bimetallic strip calculation is given in Fig. 10 along with the temperature dependence of the dimensionless curvature for four PET/graphite cross-ply composite strips. The average values for T_{start} and T_{end} from four samples were $T_{start} = 239^\circ\text{C}$ and $T_{end} = 184^\circ\text{C}$. The qualitative agreement to the theory is good down to 100°C. The good agreement shows that the rapid rise in dimensionless

TABLE I: Temperature independent parameters of the fibers and the matrix

Property	PET/Graphite Composites	J Polymer/Graphite Composites
V_f	43%	58%
v_f	57%	42%
E_L^m	220 GPa	220 GPa
E_T	14 GPa	14 GPa
α_L	$-0.45 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$	$-0.45 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$
α_T	$18 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$	$18 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$
v_f	0.20	0.20
v_f^m	0.33	0.33
T_m	239	256
T_c	184	245
T_0^{end}	239	240

curvature is caused by the large differential thermal shrinkage that occurs during crystallization. Below 100°C, the theoretical curve rises and the experimental curve drops. This discrepancy is due to the matrix cracking that occurs during the experiments. The decrease is not predicted by the theory, because the theory assumes that no cracking occurs.

We next consider J polymer/graphite cross-ply composite strips as an example of a system that does not exhibit a rapid rise in dimensionless curvature at high temperatures. The temperature independent parameters are listed in Table I. The fiber volume fraction was determined by measuring the density of the cross-ply composite strip. The temperature dependence of the storage modulus of J Polymer is given in Fig. 9. The sample used for the DMA experiment was annealed in the vacuum oven overnight at 160°C to maximize the crystallinity. The last data we need is the thermal expansion coefficient of J Polymer from the end of crystallization down to room temperature. The zero-(atmospheric) pressure volume versus temperature data during heating is given by the solid line in Fig. 6. The shoulder at 135°C is due to crystallization that takes place once the sample is heated past T_c . Its presence is due to the use of an incompletely crystallized sample. The sample completes melting at 288°C. For our predictions, we need the volume versus temperature data during cooling which we expect to follow the dotted line in Fig. 6. First J Polymer will supercool to T_c which as determined by DSC is 256°C. During crystallization which starts at 256°C and ends at 243°C, the volume will rapidly decrease eventually meeting the solid line result. Because the shoulder which appears on heating is due to using an incompletely crystallized sample, it will not appear on cooling. The volume versus temperature data below 140°C was approximated by extrapolating a line parallel to the heating data. For calculations, we use an empirical fit for the volume versus temperature data. Differentiating the results give the following empirical expression for the thermal expansion coefficient below 245°C

$$\alpha_m(T) = (519 - 5.87T + 0.018T^2) \times 10^{-6} \quad 160^\circ\text{C} < T < 245^\circ\text{C} \quad (8)$$

$$\alpha_m(T) = 113 \times 10^{-6} \quad T < 160^\circ\text{C} \quad (9)$$

A zero-parameter, modified bimetallic strip calculation is given in Fig. 11 along with the temperature dependence of the dimensionless curvature of four different J Polymer/graphite cross-ply composite strips. The theoretical result accurately predicts the experimental slopes for three of the samples. The two middle samples showed a downturn in dimensionless

Fig. 9 - Dynamic mechanical analysis of poly(ethylene terephthalate) and of J Polymer. Both samples were annealed to maximize the crystallinity.

curvature at low temperatures. These downturns are due to matrix cracking which as explained above is not included in the theory. The lowest experimental data is roughly 50% of the theoretical prediction below 150°C and shows no evidence of cracking. It is possible that internal delamination occurred and prevented the expected increase in dimensionless curvature.

These two examples show that it is possible to calculate the magnitude of residual thermal stresses in composites that have semicrystalline thermoplastic matrices. The three important matrix properties that are required in the calculation are the temperature dependence of the modulus, the temperature dependence of the zero (atmospheric)-pressure specific volume during cooling, and the temperature for the onset of residual thermal stresses. Each of these properties could be affected by processing. For example, cooling at faster rates could decrease T_c and therefore decrease the temperature for the onset of residual thermal stresses. Faster rates could also change the zero (atmospheric)-specific volume behavior, the amount and morphology of the crystallization, and the temperature dependence of the modulus. Each of these properties could also be affected by viscoelastic properties of the matrix. We have ignored the possibility of the residual thermal stresses relaxing. The magnitude of this effect can be studied by measuring changes in curvature over time. We have not yet found evidence that relaxation has a large effect.

In the experiments described here, the presence of residual thermal stresses was obvious due to observation of cross-ply composite strip curvature. The curvature developed due to a mismatch of thermal expansion properties between the zero and the 90 degree plies. Even in balanced composites, however, which do not develop curvature, there will be a significant amount of residual thermal stresses due to the mismatch of the thermal expansion properties between the matrix and the fibers. The onset of residual thermal stress build-up in balanced composites will be at the same temperature as the onset of curvature increase in unbalanced composites. Furthermore, the magnitude of h/r provides a ranking for the levels of residual thermal

Fig. 10 - Dimensionless curvature as a function of temperature while cooling for four poly(ethylene terephthalate)/graphite cross-ply composite strips and as predicted by the bimetallic strip equation.

Fig. 11 - Dimensionless curvature as a function of temperature while cooling for four J Polymer/graphite cross-ply composite strips and as predicted by the bimetallic strip equation.

stresses in balanced composites. The residual thermal stresses in the matrices we looked at rank as follows: PEEK > J Polymer > PET > nylon 66.

To minimize the magnitude of the residual thermal stresses, it is preferable to avoid increases in residual thermal stresses during crystallization. PEEK and J Polymer composites accomplish this task, but they also develop more curvature than PET or nylon 66 composites. The reason is that their thermal expansion coefficients after crystallization is complete are larger than the thermal expansion coefficients of PET and nylon 66. This point is illustrated by comparing the slopes of the PET and the J Polymer volume versus temperature data in Fig. 6. In addition, at least for PEEK, the amount of differential shrinkage is larger because the temperature range from the onset of residual thermal stresses to room temperature is larger than with the other three matrices.

Besides the magnitude of the residual thermal stresses, it is important to know how those stresses effect the matrix. In PEEK, with the largest amount of stresses we see no evidence of cracking. In J Polymer, with the next highest amount of stresses, we see only occasional evidence of cracking. In PET, however, we always see cracking. Apparently, PET cannot tolerate a very high level of stresses when constrained by fibers in a composite.

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References

1. J. A. Nairn and P. Zoller, "Matrix Solidification and the Resulting Residual Thermal Stresses in Composites," *J. Mat. Sci.*, 20 (1985) pp. 355-367.
2. J. E. Bailey, P. T. Curtis and A. Parvisi, "On the Transverse Cracking and Longitudinal Splitting of Glass and Carbon Fibre Reinforced Epoxy Cross Ply Laminates and the Effect of Poisson and Thermally Generated Strain," *Proc. Roy. Soc. London. A.*, 366 (1979) pp. 599-623.
3. F. R. Jones, A. R. Wheatley and J. E. Bailey, "The Effect of Thermal Strains on the Microcracking and Stress Corrosion Behaviour of GRP," pp. 415-429 in *Composite Structures*, I. H. Marshall, Ed.; Applied Science Publishers, Barking, United Kingdom, 1981.
4. F. R. Jones, M. Mulheron and J. E. Bailey, "Generation of Thermal Strains in GRP," *J. Mat. Sci.*, 18 (1983) pp. 1533-1539.
5. J. A. Nairn and P. Zoller, "Residual Thermal Stresses in Amorphous and Semicrystalline Thermoplastic Matrices," paper presented at ASTM Meeting on Toughened Composites, Houston, March 1985 (submitted for ASTM Special Technical Publication on Toughened Composites).
6. P. Zoller, "High Pressure Volume Dilatometry as a Thermoanalytical Technique Applied to Polymers," *Proc. Eleventh North American Thermal Analysis Soc.*, II (1981) pp. 37-42.

7. P. Zoller, P. Bolli, V. Pahud and H. Ackerman, "Apparatus for Measuring Pressure-Volume-Temperature Relations of Polymers to 350°C and 2200 kg/cm²," *Rev. Sci. Instr.*, 47 (1978) pp. 948-952.
8. S. Timoshenko, "Analysis of Bi-Metal Thermostats," *J. Opt. Soc. Amer.*, 11 (1925) pp. 233-255.
9. J. T. Hartness, "Polyetheretherketone Matrix Composites," paper presented at the 14th National SAMPE Technical Conference, October 12-14, 1982.
10. R. A. Schapery, "Thermal Expansion Coefficients of Composite Materials Based on Energy Principles," *J. Comp. Mat.*, 2 (1968) pp. 380-404.
11. J. A. Nairn, "Thermoelastic Analysis of Residual Stresses in Unidirectional, High-Performance Composites," *Polymer Composites*, in press.
12. J. J. Jones, *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, pp. 90-98; McGraw-Hill Book Co., New York, 1975.
13. J. M. Mahishi and D. F. Adams, "Fracture Behaviour of a Single-Fiber Graphite/Epoxy Model Composite Containing a Broken Fibre or Cracked Matrix," *J. Mat. Sci.*, 18 (1983) pp. 447-456.
14. D. A. Crane and D. F. Adams, "Finite Element Micromechanical Analysis of a Unidirectional Composite Including Longitudinal Shear Loading," University of Wyoming, USA, Report UWME-DR-101-101-1, 1981.
15. P. Zoller and P. Bolli, "Pressure-Volume-Temperature Relationships of Solid and Molten Poly(ethylene Terephthalate)," *J. Macromol. Sci. - Phys.*, B18 (1980) pp. 555-568.